

EXPLORING HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES AND PERFORMANCE EFFICIENCY AT PKU MUHAMMADIYAH YOGYAKARTA UNIT II

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Abstract

Background: Issues of ASEAN Free Trade Area (AFTA) and globalization of the world economy demands which is every profit and non-profit organizations to compete in marketing and resource. The changes, requires hospitals to survive among competitors that would appear at any moment. Therefore, Human Resources Management hospitals must be able to respond it.

Methods: The study design was qualitative used in-depth interviews and quantitative method for analyzing a plan about between condition HR today and the need for hospital accreditation of type B and KARS version 2012.

Results: Based on the research results, there is a shortage of human resources about the type and number according to hospital type B and for the accreditation of 99 elements document ratings are 96 % complete. As for performance assessment PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II responsibility for the examination and treatment, training, science and research, is sues of hospital management which is indispensable. To support the referral level, in terms of both treatment and prevention. As well as for international cooperation needs to be improved. While the assessment of training needs at the level of priority on the entire item, respondents give a high priority level assessment.

Conclusion: There is a shortage of the type and quantity of human resources between the condition of human resources today and the provisions of hospital type B and there are some completeness of documents for the accreditation of qualifications assessment and education staff KARS 2012 version.

Keywords: Hospital Performances, Human Resources Management

INTRODUCTION

Issues of ASEAN Free Trade Area (AFTA) and globalization of the world economy demands which is every profit and non-profit organizations to compete in marketing and resource. This situation also applies to the hospital industry. The changes, requires hospitals to survive among competitors that would appear at any moment. Therefore, Human Resources (HR) hospitals must be able to respond it. HR needs proper planning in accordance with the service requirements of each unit in accordance with the classification of hospitals based on the Regulation of the Minister of Health (Permenkes) number 56 of 2014 as well as national accreditation

standard version of the Commission on Accreditation of Hospitals 2012 (KARS). So RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II will head the hospital type B and accreditation standards in 2012, especially chapter version KARS Qualifications and Education Staff

B. Subject and Object Research

The whole personnel who were in the RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II and the medical committee, Bottom managers, Secretariat, and staffing

C. Data Collection Techniques

In collecting the data, the authors use the method as follows:

- a. Primary data obtained from observation, interviews consisted of bottom managers, Secretariat, staffing and committee chairman RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Medical Unit II.
- b. Secondary data from the data of the hospital is used as a secondary data relating to research subjects on the number and kinds and competence of medical personnel in RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II .
- c. Analysis of data collection.

RESULTS

Tabel Results of Interviews on Hospital type B and Accreditation KARS version 2012

1. What's your plan about the human resource in the hospital PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II at this time to go to the Hospital of type B and accreditation KARS version 2012?

Informant 1	Informant 2
"To go to the hospital type B, human conditions that exist today have not been 100 percent to meet the rules of Permenkes 56 /2014, for a general dentist, doctor sub specialists still lacking "	"There are still some processes, especially the less common dentists and physicians sub specialists", for accreditation there's no problem about staying adapted to check"

2. What have to do by RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II with strength conditions that exist today?

Informant 1	Informant 2
" The existing human resources we still give appropriate competence training “	" For power that exists today , hospital training and to improve the quality workshop "

3. How do you do for the planning for hospital types B and accreditation KARS version 2012 whether there are additional types of services to other specialists?

Informant 1	Informant 2

“clearly there are additional services”	" There will be the addition of services will be tailored to the needs "
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Analysis of the interviews on the planning of the Human Resources Unit RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta II towards hospital type B and accreditation version KARS 2012.

From interviews, both first and second informant told to go to the hospital if type B according to the rules Permenkes 56 in 2014, the condition of the existing human resources in PKU Muhammadiyah Hospital Yogyakarta Unit II is still understaffed namely dentists and sub. Specialists. But the hospital has done some processes such as recruitment. The team already knows the problem towards hospital type B and accreditation so they can more focused on it.

Analysis of the interviews about hospital and conditions that exist today.

Based on the interview, the informant 1 and 2 say if that should be done by the hospital associated with pre-existing conditions at this time is to provide training to existing employees. It is recognized by both informants is crucial to improving the quality of human resources at their disposal.

Analysis of the results of interviews regarding additional medical services related to hospital planning and accreditation of type B KARS version 2012.

Both informants explained if additional services closely related to hospital planning toward type B and accreditation KARS version 2012 in which hospitals are required to provide services and medical needs are adapted to hospital type B based Permenkes 56 in 2014 and 2012 accreditation KARS version.

Analysis of conditions Human Resources Managemen (HRM) PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II.

From the analysis of the situation Human Resources conditions in RS PKU

Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II at the present time, RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II have pursued these shortage in order to hospital type B. Currently, the hospital is still experiencing a shortage of doctors spesialist anatomic pathology are two, medical rehabilitation specialist is one, sub physician specialist in obstetrics and gynecology specialist. One person at the doctor sub specialist in internal medicine, sub physician specialists in pediatric, and general dentists also 1 person. To the shortage of doctors is RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II has been doing some recruitment. As for human resources in addition to doctors , some are still experiencing a shortage of medical personnel such as pharmacists for outpatient is one, pharmacist department emergency department is one, ICU pharmacist is one , pharmaceutical technical personnel installation section emergency are two people , and technical personnel pharmacy ICU is one person. Shortages that occurred in RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta

Unit II because the number of pharmacists are still few and some of pharmacists and concurrent tasks between outpatient and inpatient care, where it is made ineffective. RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II had planned fatherly recruitment of pharmacists and pharmacy technical personnel. This power is needed to push the

existing hospital. Overseas recruitment and qualification processes for HR personnel PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II have been implemented, this process is expected may be submitted as a requirement for hospital type B which has been planned RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II will be submitted in May 2015.

Analysis of Qualification and Education staff Assessment by KARS accreditation version 2012.

Human Resources Management (HRM) is an important part of a hospital. The success and the success of the hospital depends how the existing human resources for HR is driving hospital services. One way to assess the quality and quality of human resources by using the national standards of accreditation KARS 2012 version that has been adapted from the International standard JCI. Hospital Accreditation is a quality improvement program undertaken by building systems and quality culture. Through the hospital accreditation will be no improvement in the hospital system that includes input, process and output. Standard input RS consisting of facilities and human resources to be met by the RS while the standard process that consists of the availability of policy guidelines, procedures and evidence of implementation of activities should be well documented. Standard output is measured by the performance of RS quality indicators should also be documented continuously. The accreditation process itself acquired through sharing stages namely the existence of hospital policy, guidance to the collection of documents for later formed an SOP that will be disseminated to all hospital personnel in order to be implemented. Based on the document search and competency qualification assessment and accreditation of education staff in order KARS 2012 version at RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II found some still in the process of drafting documents such as the assessment element KPS Planning chapter 5 where in item 2 that the personnel file that contains the qualifying staff and in item 3 that the personnel file containing job descriptions of staff members, RS PKU Muhammadiyah is still in process of drafting the document. Also in chapter 8.4 KPS assessment of element orientation and education where the item 4 the existence of a policy regarding the provision of vaccination and immunization staff and in item 5 is the existence of a policy on evaluation, counseling, and follow up about staff whose exposed communicable diseases coordinated with infection prevention and control program, RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II is still in the process of completing documents. Manager's said that the guidelines for elements 8.4 have not been ratified so that in the process of manufacture of SOP is still hampered. In the 11 chapters of PPP assessment element of monitoring and evaluation of the medical staff members also found some items that are still in the process in peyusunan document, is item 1 on evaluation of professional practice that will continually the quality and safety of patient care provided by each member of the medical staff checked and delivered to members of the medical staff at least once a year, on item 2 is regarding the evaluation of professional practice in ongoing and annual inspection of each medical staff member is achieved through a uniform process established by the policy of the hospital and on item three i.e. the evaluation that considers and uses a comparative basis proactive as a comparison to literature based treatment. In the 12 chapters of PPP assessment element of verification and evaluation of credentials, there are 2 items that are still in the process of arranging the documents on item 5 that the hospital has a process to ensure that credentialing of nurses contract are valid and complete before assignment and at item 6 the hospital has a process for ensure the validity of the credentials of nurses who are not employees of the hospital, but the accompanying doctor and provide

services to hospital patients. As well as the assessment element KPS 15 chapters other professional health staff item 6 which hospitals have processes in place to ensure that other staff who are not employees of the hospital but doctors assist and provide services to hospital patients have valid credentials comparable to the requirements of hospitals, still in the process of drafting the document. Expected completion penyusunan documents RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II is completed before the month of May 2015, therefore the accreditation team will be filed in the month of June 2015. In accordance with what the general overview in chapter qualification and accreditation of educational staff KARS 2012 version that hospitals require a variety of skills and qualified staff to carry out the mission of the hospital and meet patient needs. Hospital leader work together to determine the number and type of staff needed based on the recommendations of the working units and service director. Recruitment, evaluation and assignment of staff to do as well as possible through a coordinated and efficient.

Assessment of Performance of PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II in Responsibility of Examination and Treatment.

In granting this questionnaire involves all employees of RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II. Respondents were willing to follow the study and in accordance with the criteria inklusi as many as 93 respondents out of the total 110 respondents. Of the 93 respondents are dominated by female respondents as many as 68 respondents. This is caused by the majority of employees in

RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II is dominated by women. According Muchlas (2008) sex in general there is no significant differences in the productivity of labor Education level PKU Muhammadiyah Hospital employees who were respondents in this study are mostly diploma that as many as 50 respondents. Characteristics of individuals that education is becoming an important source of status in the organization of work. Education followed the ladder is a draw of high status. The higher educations are achieved a great desire to take advantage of the capabilities and skills in achieving a higher position in the organization (Siagian, 2002). Respondents in this study, there were 79 respondents who are in the working area of the nurses, this is because the number of nurses more than any other power which the number of nurses has been adapted to the number of beds. Whereas in this study the number of respondents with the status as a permanent employee that is 59 respondents. Status of permanent employee will give special meaning to the person's work performance and productivity. With the status of permanent employee, will provide increased responsibility, making the job will still be more valuable and so important that good performance can be maintained. According to Ilyas (1999), performance assessment is an evaluation of the job performance of personnel by comparing it to the gold standard appearance. From assessment, the assessor can determine whether the work performed is in accordance with the job description as a benchmark assessment. Ilyas (1999) said that an assessment of performance should be based on the behavior of personnel associated with work as well as expected results of the work process. A company or organization requires any personnel to work hard in accordance with established standards. In the performance assessment, workers' traits, character and personality of the personnel that are unique and very personal nature are not included in the assessment criteria. In the questionnaire that was distributed to the respondents for the assessment of hospital performance PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II regarding responsibility for the examination and treatment

as much as 31 respondents provide an assessment that is urgently needed, it means that the services on the examination and treatment which is the cornerstone of a hospital realized by employees of RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II is indispensable in his responsibilities. It shows if the hospital and its employees have contributed to share responsibility in the examination and treatment services.

Performance Assessment PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II in Responsibility of Exercise.

A total of 32 respondents provide an assessment of the performance of RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II of the responsibility for training that is very necessary. Exercise for employees is indispensable in order to develop human resources. Education and training can be seen as a form of investment. Therefore, any organization or agency that wants to expand, the education and training of employees must obtain the most attention

Performance Assessment PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II in Responsibility of Science and Research.

A total of 26 respondents provide an assessment of the performance of RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II of the responsibility for science and research knowledge is indispensable. This forms the basis for employees to develop competencies and to increase knowledge by doing the kinds of research that is facilitated by the hospital so that in line with what is needed between the hospital and its employees.

Performance Assessment PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II in Responsibility of Support Reference Rate.

A total of 19 respondents provide an assessment of the performance of RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II of the responsibility to support the referral is indispensable. The BJPS (A new Medicare System in Indonesia) insurances indispensable reference support where it can assist the hospital in providing services appropriate competence and affects the quality of medical service to be provided.

Assessment of Performance PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II Responsibility of Therapy and Prevention.

One of the goals the hospital is to provide treatment and prevention services, it is recognized by both the hospital and the employee. So that as many as 24 respondents rate the indispensable responsibility towards treatment and prevention. This is a good step in order to develop the hospital.

Performance Assessment PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II in Responsibility of International Cooperation.

A total of 29 respondents provide an assessment of the needs to be improved on the responsibility of the international cooperation, this partnership is intended to hospitals always develop health services so that it can participate in the progress of the world as well as hospitalization, especially in the field of human resources

Performance Assessment PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II in Responsibility of the Issues at Hospital Management And Healthy.

Performance assessment responsibility for issues of hospital management and healthcare as much as 22 respondents assess if the issue of hospital management and health that is indispensable there, with good response

hospital is expected to evolve and be more prudent in deciding a case because the hospital has been treating issues and health management in hospitals

Training Needs Assessment with Priority Levels PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II against Timely Skills and Work Plan.

A total of 75 respondents give a high priority for assessment of training needs for timely skills and work plans. This will have a great impact on the culture of discipline employees RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II, where the presence of the discipline then productivity will increase. Discipline is one of the most important operative functions and cannot be ignored because as part of the maintenance function of the employee, and where better work discipline of employees, higher performance can be achieved (Sastrohadiwiyo, 2005).

CONCLUSION

- a. Human Resources (HR) at RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II at the present time is still lacking, both in terms of the number of HR and HR characteristics.
- b. In terms of the number and type of human resources there is a shortage of medical personnel to get to the RS type B.
- c. For accreditation KARS version 2012, regarding the assessment of qualification and education staff of 99 elements of appraisal, there are 4 elements are still in the process of document completeness. This means that there are 96 % complete documents.
- d. From the analysis of the performance assessment questionnaire regarding RS PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II responsibility for the examination and treatment, training, science and research, issues of hospital management which is indispensable. To support the referral, in terms of both treatment and prevention. As well as for international cooperation needs to be improved.
- e. From the results of the questionnaire on the analysis of training needs assessment with the priority level of PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II of the health policy and strategy and national health programs, functions, responsibilities and duties hospitals, timely skills and work plan, the skills to identify and solve the problem, the skills to search for information and use information for decision-making, as well as the skills to organize and lead meetings /workshops is a high priority.

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